

Enhancing the Aquaculture Programme in India: A Step toward Sustainable Development

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Abstract

Aquaculture or fish farming is a vital source of food and commercial products and contributing to healthier threatens species. It is a practice of breeding, raising and harvesting of fishes, shell fishes, crustaceans and aquatic plants on controlled environments like pond, tanks or oceans waters. The most common practice of aquaculture is fish farming. The Blue Revolution Scheme has helped increase aquaculture production and fisheries production in India using multi-dimensional activities.

Keywords: Aquaculture, Sustainable, Blue Revolution, and Fish.

1. Introduction:

Harvesting of aquatic organisms has been practiced through the ages and it is speculated that such practices may have remote roots in highly organized ancient water-oriented civilizations. There are various reports of artificial propagation of fishes in china in fifth century B.C. as fish was an important dietary component and oyster culture in ancient Rome and Gaul. Husbandry of aquatic animals or aquaculture is the growing of aquatic organisms under controlled conditions provides a unique contribution to nutrition in several regions of the world because of its extremely high productivity and first-class protein crops rather than starch stapled food. Aquaculture is by no means restricted to food production. Today aquaculture serve wide varieties such as shrimp culture, mussel culture, pearl culture, frog culture and even economically important weeds etc.

The fishery resources in India consist of 1.6 million hectares of tanks and ponds, 3.0 million hectares of reservoirs, 2.0 million hectares of brackish water areas and about 2.0 million square

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kilometers of marine area in the form of EEZ (Exclusive Economic Zone). Beside there are 27 thousand kilometers of rivers and canal systems. Every year several tanks and reservoirs are being constructed for irrigation and power generation. About 5.0 million tons of fish production in our country is expected by the beginning of this century.

Fish culture in India is an age-old practice. In village areas tanks and ponds are mainly used for irrigation or drinking water. By stocking fast growing carps, rich crop of fish can be harvested, otherwise the water body remains as unproductive area.

Fish production in the ponds was of the order of 600 kg /ha/yr. The reason for low production is non stocking or less stocking of fast-growing carp seed, due to non-availability of quality seed in adequate quantity and unscientific management of ponds. With the successful breeding of major carps by hypophysation in 1957 by Hiralal Choudhary and K.H Alikunhi and subsequent standardisation of induced breeding technology, by use of HCG, homoeopathic drugs and ovaprim etc. has resulted in assured seed production.

By introducing integrated fish culture technology and by recycling organic wastes, higher yield of fish is achieved with lesser financial expenditure. The entrepreneur is assured of getting not only good crop of fish but additional income from other systems of cultures. In dairy cum fisheries, sale of milk provides additional incomes whereas cattle dung is used as fertilizer for tank. In poultry cum fisheries sale of eggs and chicken meat provides additional income whereas poultry litters can be used as a fertilizer for tank. In piggery cum fisheries, pork fetches good income, whereas pig dung is good manure for the tank.

2. Observation:

Global fisheries and aquaculture production reached a historic high of 223.2 million metric tonnes (MMT) in the fiscal year 2022. This figure includes 185.4 MMT of aquatic animals (live weight equivalent) and 37.8 MMT of algae (wet weight). China remained the major producer (36%), followed by India (8%), Indonesia (7%), Viet Nam (5 %) and Peru (3 %).

World aquaculture production reached a new record of 130.9 million tonnes in 2022, valued at USD 313 billion and comprising 94.4 million tonnes of aquatic animals and 36.5 million

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tonnes of algae. Asia contributed 91.4% of the overall total, followed by Latin America and the Caribbean (3.3%), Europe (2.7%), Africa (1.9%), Northern America (0.5%) and Oceania (0.2%). Ten leading countries (China, Indonesia, India, Vietnam, Bangladesh, Philippines, Republic of Korea, Norway, Egypt and Chile) produced 89.8 % of the total. In 2022, production of animal species from aquaculture (51 percent) surpassed for the first time that from capture fisheries, with inland aquaculture producing 62.6 percent of total farmed aquatic animals.

Table 1. Fish Production in India

Year	Fish Production (In lakh Tonnes)			Annual Average Growth Rate (Percent)		
	Marine	Inland	Total	Marine	Inland	All India
2010 -11	32.5	49.81	82.31	4.7	1.78	2.91
2011 -12	33.72	52.94	86.66	3.75	6.28	5.28
2012 - 13	33.21	57.19	90.4	-1.51	8.03	4.32
2013 -14	34.43	61.36	95.79	3.67	7.29	5.96
2014 -15	35.69	66.91	102.6	3.66	9.04	7.11
2015 -16	36.0	71.62	107.62	0.87	7.04	4.89
2016 - 17	36.25	78.06	114.31	1.14	8.63	6.12
2017 –18	37.56	89.48	127.04	3.61	14.62	11.13
2018 -19	38.53	97.2	135.73	2.58	8.62	6.84
2019 -20	37.27	104.37	141.64	-3.2	7.37	4.35
2020 - 21	34.76	112.49	147.25	-6.7	7.80	4.0
2021 - 22	41.27	121.21	162.48	18.7	7.76	10.34

Data from Handbook on fisheries statistics 2022

India is the second largest fish producing country in the world and accounts for 8 % of the global production. The total fish production during FY 2023-24 is estimated at 18.40 MMT with a contribution of 13.91 MMT from Inland sector and 4.49 MMT from Marine sector. The fisheries sector plays an important role in the national economy with the share of Fisheries sector in the total Gross Value Added (GVA), at constant prices, in 2022-23 is estimated at Rs. 1,65,075 Crores that

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constitutes about 1.12% of the total national GVA and 7.26% of agricultural GVA. The sector has shown an impressive growth rate of 7.58% (Constant Price: 2011-12) during the year 2021- 22 to 2022-23. However, the annual average growth rate in the Fisheries sector has been 6.30% over the last five years. During FY 2023-24, export of marine products stood at 1.78 MMT and valued at Rs. 60,523.89 Crores (USD: 7.38 billion) with an annual growth rate of about 2.67% (in Quantity).

The leading states in the production of fish during 2022-23 were Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Karnataka, Odisha, Kerala, and Uttar Pradesh whereas the highest-ranking states for yearly fish consumption (per capita/kg) were Andaman & Nicobar Islands (114), Lakshadweep (89), and Tripura (27.62). During this period, India has a total of 1897 ice plants with a combined production capacity of 29.5 lakh tonnes and the leading states are Gujarat, Kerala, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh and West Bengal. As per MPEDA, India has a well-established fish processing infrastructure, with a total of 637 plants across the country and capable of processing 36.79 thousand MT. The top five regions with the highest concentration of processing plants and storage facilities are Kochi, Veraval, Mangalore, Mumbai, and Kolkata.

3. Discussion:

The scope of aquaculture is vast and multifaceted, contributing significantly to Food Production: Aquaculture provides a sustainable source of protein rich food, helping meet the increasing demand for sea food.

Economic Growth: Aquaculture contributes to national income , foreign exchange earnings and rural development.

Employment: The sector support millions of people involved in fishing, processing and marketing.

The programme like Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana (PMMSY) is one of the major aims to transform India into a leading hub for fish and aquatic product.

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